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**LMR AS A STRATEGIC TOOL FOR EXPANDING THE EXPORT POTENTIAL AND
STRENGTHENING THE FINANCIAL AND ECONOMIC POSITIONS OF THE
RUSSIAN FUEL AND ENERGY COMPLEX**

The era of global energy transformation has necessitated decarbonization, diversification of the energy balance and ensuring energy security, forming a steady interest in new nuclear technologies, among which low-power modular reactors (LMR) occupy a special place. LMR has the potential not only to diversify Russia's export portfolio, but also to become a key factor in strengthening its financial and economic position. The research of the article is aimed at a comprehensive study of the prospects for the development and international promotion of the LMR, as one of the key areas of technological and export modernization

of the Russian nuclear power industry, and strengthening its financial and economic positions in the global energy markets. The study reveals the key directions and mechanisms for promoting small modular reactors (LMR) in the international arena, their role in shaping a sustainable export flow, competitive advantages, the possibility of integration with renewable energy sources as part of hybrid energy systems, as well as the role of LMR in attracting investments and strengthening Russia's financial and economic position in the global energy sector. Special attention is paid to the analysis of pilot projects (for example, Shelekhovsky in Yakutia), export initiatives of Rosatom State Corporation, and interstate mechanisms for promoting LMR in the markets of Asia, the Arctic, Africa, and Latin America. It is concluded that realizing the potential of the LMR requires systemic government support, institutional flexibility, and international partnership. The promotion of small reactors can not only strengthen Russia's export position, but also contribute to the formation of a new architecture for decentralized and environmentally sound energy supply, as well as become a financial and economic driver capable of diversifying Russia's export portfolio, increasing foreign exchange earnings, strengthening national energy security and increasing the country's competitiveness in the global energy market.

Keywords: low-power modular reactors (LMR), export potential, energy markets, international cooperation, nuclear energy, financial and economic strategy, investments, innovative technologies, competitiveness, sustainable development, de-risking, globalization.

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Малый размер

Физически представляет собой лишь малую часть обычного ядерного реактора.

Модульность

Позволяет собирать системы и компоненты на заводе и доставлять их в собранном виде на место установки.

Ядерное деление

Использует ядерное деление для выработки тепла и получения энергии.

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: NuScale Power (77), GE
Hitachi (BWRX-300), Holtec TerraPower.

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6.		(ATOMEXPO, IAEA General Conference).	- -

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